

Fluoro Complexes of Hexavalent Uranium

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Fluoro compounds of hexavalent uranium are of special interest because of their use in atomic energy programme. In the literature a few fluoro complexes of UO_2^{++} have been reported. Equilibrium constants for the formation of the complexes, $\text{UO}_2^{++} + n\text{F}^- \rightarrow \text{UO}_2\text{F}_n^{2-n}$, having the maximum value of $n = 3$, have been determined potentiometrically by Ahrland and Larsson¹. The presence of the species UO_2F^+ , UO_2F_2 and $\text{UO}_2\text{F}_4^{2-}$ has been confirmed spectrophotometrically by Blake *et al.*², although Day and Powers³ could find no evidence for a complex with $n > 1$. A number of double fluorides are formed with other metal fluorides. These include $3\text{KF} \cdot \text{UO}_2\text{F}_2$, $3\text{NH}_4\text{F} \cdot \text{UO}_2\text{F}_2$, $\text{NaF} \cdot \text{UO}_2\text{F}_2$, $3\text{KF} \cdot 2\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2$, $5\text{KF} \cdot \text{UO}_2\text{F}_2$ etc.⁴. The X-ray crystallographic analysis of $3\text{KF} \cdot \text{UO}_2\text{F}_2$ indicates⁴ the presence of $(\text{UO}_2\text{F}_5)^{3-}$ units. The electrical conductivity of $3\text{KF} \cdot \text{UO}_2\text{F}_2$ in solution has been interpreted by Miolati *et al.*⁵ in favour of the existence of $(\text{UO}_2\text{F}_5)^{3-}$ ion, whereas spectrophotometric studies by Blake *et al.*² indicated the presence of $(\text{UO}_2\text{F}_4)^{2-}$ ion. Olsson⁶ reported the isolation of a few complex salts of the three types $\text{BHF} \cdot n\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2$ where $n = 1, 2$ and 3 and B is an organic base. No studies have been made on the structures or properties of the compounds and the nature of the complex ions present in these compounds is not definitely known. These facts have prompted us to undertake a detailed study on the fluoro complexes of UO_2^{++} . In the present communication we are reporting the isolation of a number of such complexes with organic and inorganic complex cations.

For the preparation of the complex salts with organic basic cations, concentrated solutions of the bases in 20% HF were added all at a time to a concentrated solution of UO_2F_2 in 20% HF. In most cases the crystalline precipitates appeared immediately, but in a few cases vigorous scratching was necessary for precipitation. The precipitates were washed successively with dilute HF, water, ethanol and acetone and then dried over H_2SO_4 . The compounds were tried with three different molar ratios of UO_2F_2 and base, *viz.*, 1 : 1, 1 : 3 and 3 : 1. In most cases the same type of compound, $\text{BH}[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]$ or $\text{BH}[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained irrespective of the relative concentrations. Quinoline, however, gave $\text{QH}[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]$ with U : B ratio 1 : 1 or 1 : 3, but a compound of the type $[\text{BH}(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_5]$ was obtained with U : quinoline ratio 3 : 1. With dipyrindyl, only U : dipyrindyl = 1 : 1 ratio gave pure compound with formula $\text{BH}[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. Dimethyl aniline gave $[\text{BH}(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_5]$ type compound with all the three concentrations. The latter type of compounds belongs to the second series of compounds ($\text{BHF} \cdot 2\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2$) described by Olsson⁶.

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The analytical data of the compounds prepared with organic bases are given in Table 1.

For the preparation of complex salts with inorganic complex cations, aqueous solutions of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$ and $[\text{Coen}_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ (both *cis*- and *trans*-) were added to 20% HF solution of UO_2F_2 . The precipitates were washed and dried as before. Analysis of the compounds with the latter precipitant corresponded to the formulation $[\text{Coen}_2\text{Cl}_2][\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]$, while the precipitate with $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$ corresponded to the composition $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{F}_3 \cdot 2\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2$.

Analysis of the compound with *cis*- $[\text{Coen}_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$:

U, 41.5; Cl, 12.1; F, 9.98%

of the compound with *trans*- $[\text{Coen}_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$:

U, 41.5; Cl, 12.1; F, 10.5%

of the compound with $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$:

Co, 7.26; U, 56.8; N, 10.3; F, 16.3%

TABLE 1

Compounds Prepared	%U	%F	%N	%C	%H
1. α -PicH $[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]$	Calc. 56.53 Found 56.3	Calc. 13.54 Found 14.3	Calc. 3.33 Found 3.24	Calc. 17.10 Found 17.3	Calc. 1.90 Found 2.15
2. Dipy.H. $[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Calc. 47.42 Found 47.7	Calc. 11.36 Found 12.3	Calc. 5.58 Found 5.38		
3. Ox.H. $[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]$	Calc. 50.8 Found 49.5	Calc. 12.1 Found 12.1	Calc. 3.0 Found 3.11	Calc. 22.83 Found 22.5	Calc. 1.69 Found 1.95
4. <i>o</i> -Phen.H. $[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Calc. 45.25 Found 45.2	Calc. 10.83 Found 10.4	Calc. 5.32 Found 5.50		
5. α -Naph.H. $[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Calc. 48.67 Found 48.33	Calc. 11.66 Found 12.2			
6. β -Naph.H. $[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]$	Calc. 50.54 Found 50.4	Calc. 12.11 Found 13.0			
7. Anth.H. $[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]$	Calc. 51.18 Found 51.4	Calc. 12.26 Found 13.5	Calc. 3.01 Found 2.68		
8. <i>p</i> -Amino.phen.H. $[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]$	Calc. 54.46 Found 54.0	Calc. 13.04 Found 13.3	Calc. 3.20 Found 2.96		
9. Nic.H. $[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]$	Calc. 52.77 Found 53.1	Calc. 12.64 Found 12.8			
10. QH $[\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]$	Calc. 52.08 Found 51.5	Calc. 12.47 Found 13.3			
11. QH $[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_5]$	Calc. 62.22 Found 61.5	Calc. 12.42 Found 13.0			
12. Dimethy.H. $[(\text{UO}_2)_2\text{F}_5]$	Calc. 62.74 Found 61.86	Calc. 12.69 Found 12.65			

Abbreviations : α -Pic = α -picoline; Dipy. = 2,2'-dipyridyl; Ox = 8-hydroxy quinoline; *o*-Phen = 1,10-phenanthroline; α -Naph = α -naphthyl amine; β -Naph = β -naphthyl amine; Anth = anthranilic acid; *p*-Amino phen = *p*-aminophenol; Nic = nicotinic acid; Q = quinoline; Dimethy₂ = dimethyl aniline.

Calcd. for $[\text{Coen}_2\text{Cl}_2][\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]$:

U, 41.25; Cl, 12.14; F, 9.88%

for $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{F}_3 \cdot 2\text{UO}_2\text{F}_2$:

Co, 7.07; U, 57.07; N, 10.07; F, 15.95%.

It appears that the compound with $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ is a double salt of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][\text{UO}_2\text{F}_3]_3[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6][\text{UO}_2\text{F}_5]$.

The compounds in general have the characteristic yellow colour of the uranyl compounds, except where the cation is coloured, *e.g.*, compounds with α - and β -naphthyl amine, *p*-amino phenol, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$, *cis*- and *trans*- $[\text{Coen}_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ are coloured pinkish white, pale yellow, ash, brownish yellow, green and violet respectively. In general the compounds have low solubility in water and in aqueous HF (the compounds with α -picoline, nicotinic acid, *p*-amino phenol and anthranilic acid are appreciably soluble in water and aqueous HF) and almost insoluble in organic solvents like ethanol and acetone.

Uranium was estimated by igniting the compounds to U_3O_8 and fluorine was estimated gravimetrically as PbClF in the water extract after fusing the compounds with NaOH . The compounds containing cobalt were heated to fumes with H_2SO_4 , uranium precipitated by NH_3 gas and the precipitate ignited to U_3O_8 . In the filtrate cobalt was estimated gravimetrically as CoSO_4 . C, H and N were determined by standard micro chemical methods.

The thermal decomposition of the compounds and studies on the nature of the complex ions in the compounds are being pursued, details of which will be published later on.

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